

Microbial Bioleaching of Critical Metals from Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries: A Biohydrometallurgical Approach

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3.1.3. XRD Analysis of the Black Mass

The crystalline phases present in the spent LCO-derived black mass were identified by XRD (Figure S1a). Analysis reveals distinct reflections associated with the active cathode materials LiCoO₂ and LiNiO₂, as well as the anode material graphite, and minor contributions from metallic current-collector components. LiCoO₂ is characterized by a prominent peak at $2\theta \approx 19^\circ$, with additional reflections at approximately 37.5° , 39.5° , 45.3° and 49.5° , whereas LiNiO₂ exhibits its primary peak at 18.8° alongside secondary reflections at 36.9° , 38.9° and 44.5° . The higher intensity of LiCoO₂ peaks compared with LiNiO₂ is consistent with the compositional data (Table 1), confirming that cobalt-bearing phases dominate the cathode fraction. However, the presence of well-defined LiNiO₂ reflections confirms that the investigated material represents a cobalt-dominant mixed layered oxide cathode system rather than a strictly pure LiCoO₂ phase. Both LiCoO₂ and LiNiO₂ exhibit characteristic diffraction features of layered rhombohedral $R\bar{3}m$ structures, which are typical for stoichiometric and Li-deficient layered lithium transition-metal oxides used in commercial LIBs. The most intense reflection in the diffractogram occurs at $2\theta \approx 26.6^\circ$, corresponding to the (002) plane of graphite, reflecting the high abundance of graphitic carbon originating from the anode. Additional graphite reflections at 38.9° , 44.6° and 54.7° confirm the presence of a highly crystalline hexagonal graphite phase. The dominance of the graphite peak is expected given that pyrolyzed industrial black mass retains anode carbon almost quantitatively. Weak reflections attributable to Cu and Al were also detected, originating from fragmented current collectors, an observation consistent with industrial pre-treatment studies of LCO-derived battery waste [7,35,36].

The XRD patterns of the bioleached residues reveal pronounced changes compared to the initial black mass (Figure S1b). The most intense diffraction peak, located at approximately 26° (2θ), is attributed to graphite, originating from the black mass and remaining in the solid residue after bioleaching. However, the reduced apparent intensity of this graphite reflection relative to the initial material is likely not due to graphite dissolution, but rather to (i) surface coverage or partial encapsulation of graphite particles by secondary precipitates and (ii) an increase in the amorphous fraction of the residue, which is reflected by an elevated background and increased noise in the diffractogram. In addition, several diffraction features indicate the presence of hydrated iron sulfate phases in the residue. These are evidenced by a characteristic doublet around $28\text{--}29^\circ$ (2θ), as well as additional reflections near 15° and 17° (2θ). The formation of such Fe-sulfate precipitates is consistent with bioleaching conditions and can significantly affect the relative intensities of crystalline phases by partially masking underlying reflections, including those of graphite. Notably, cobalt oxide phases are not detected in the bioleached residue. This absence is attributed to the effective dissolution of cobalt-containing

phases during bioleaching. Any remaining cobalt-bearing compounds are expected to be present only in trace amounts, below the detection limit of XRD. Overall, the XRD results indicate that bioleaching leads to the selective removal of metal-bearing phases, while the solid residue is dominated by graphite and secondary iron sulfate precipitates with a partially amorphous character. Such behavior is well documented in biohydrometallurgical leaching of LCO-based cathodes at Fe-rich conditions [6,9,14,20,23,26].

(a)

(b)

Figure S1. (a) XRD diffraction pattern of the black mass.; (b) XRD diffraction pattern of the bioleached residues.

SEM-EDS Analysis of the Bioleached Residue

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed to complement the XRD characterization of the bioleached residues. Representative SEM images (Figure S2a) reveal etched particle surfaces, increased porosity, and the presence of fine-grained secondary precipitates partially covering graphite lamellae. These morphological features are consistent with selective dissolution of metal-bearing cathode phases and the persistence of the carbonaceous matrix.

To further investigate the composition of the secondary precipitates, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was conducted on selected regions of the residue. A representative spectrum (Figure S2b) collected from an Fe-rich area is shown together with its quantitative elemental analysis (Table S1). The EDS results indicate that Fe and S are the dominant elements in the analyzed region, with Fe exceeding 70 wt%, confirming the formation of Fe-rich secondary sulfate phases under acidic, iron-driven bioleaching conditions.

Cobalt was detected only at trace levels (<2 wt%) in the analyzed areas (Table S1), indicating substantial depletion of the original Co-bearing oxide phases after leaching. While minor residual cobalt below the detection limit of XRD cannot be completely excluded, the combined XRD (Figure S1b) and SEM–EDS results consistently support effective mobilization of cobalt during bioleaching.

Figure S2. (a) SEM micrograph of the bioleached residue obtained at 1% pulp density and 20% v/v inoculum after 7 days of bioleaching. The image shows etched surfaces and Fe-rich secondary precipitates partially covering graphite lamellae.; (b) Representative EDS spectrum (Spectrum 2) collected from an Fe-rich region of the bioleached residue shown in Figure S2a.

Table S1. Quantitative elemental composition of the analyzed Fe-rich residue area (Spectrum 2).

Element	Weight %	Atomic %
P	3.09	4.13
S	20.22	26.20
K	2.05	2.17
Fe	72.80	54.03
Co	1.84	1.29

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